

Supplementary material: A high-resolution monitoring approach of urban CO₂ fluxes.

Part 1 - bottom-up model development

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Land cover types and tree species in the study area

Table S.1. Land cover type fractions of the study area.

Land cover types		Area		
		ha	%	
Impervious Surfaces	Buildings	289	32	
	Roads	115	13	66
	Paved	195	21	
Pervious Surfaces	Trees	110	12	
	Low vegetation/Soil	137	15	34
	Water	59	7	

Table S.2. List of the most abundant tree genera and species in the study area according to the local authorities' database (Baumkataster, 2021). The number of registered trees of each genus is presented along with the respective percentages. Evergreen species are noted with an asterisk. In total, 6.9 % of the registered trees are evergreen.

Genus	Representative species	No.	%	Cumulative %
<i>Tilia</i>	<i>euchlora, cordata, tomentosa, platyphyllos</i>	2363	20.2	20.2
<i>Acer</i>	<i>platanoides, campestre, pseudoplatanus, cappadocicum</i>	2084		
<i>Aesculus</i>	<i>hippocastanum</i>	1611	17.8	38.0
<i>Platanus</i>	<i>hispanica</i>	744	13.8	51.8
<i>Quercus</i>	<i>robur, cerris, pubescens, petraea, rubra</i>	520	6.4	58.2
<i>Fraxinus</i>	<i>angustifolia, excelsior, ornus</i>	409	4.4	62.6
<i>Pinus</i>	<i>angustifolia, excelsior, ornus</i>	409	3.5	66.1
<i>Pinus</i>	<i>nigra*, sylvestris*</i>	388	3.3	69.4
<i>Prunus</i>	<i>serrulata, avium, sargentii, cerasifera</i>	283	2.4	71.8
<i>Taxus</i>	<i>baccata*</i>	280	2.4	74.2
<i>Carpinus</i>	<i>betulus</i>	265	2.3	76.5

Meteorological stations

Table S.3. Meteorological stations and variables that are used as inputs to the models.

Station acronym	Geographic location	Variables	Sensor type - model	Sensor height (m a.g.l.)
BKLI	47.56173 °N, 7.58049 °E	Air temperature	Thermo-HYGrometer (Thygan)	38
		Vapor pressure	Thermo-HYGrometer (Thygan)	38
		Direct radiation	Pyrheliometer (CHP1, Kipp & Zonen)	21
		Diffuse radiation	Pyranometer (CM21, Kipp & Zonen)	21
BKFP	47.56595 °N, 7.56921 °E	Soil temperature-moisture	Thermistor - Water content reflectometer (CS655, Campbell Scientific Inc.)	-0.1
		Soil temperature-moisture	Thermistor - Water content reflectometer (CS655, Campbell Scientific Inc.)	-0.1
BSMP	47.5529 °N, 7.57456 °E	Soil temperature-moisture	Thermistor - Water content reflectometer (CS655, Campbell Scientific Inc.)	-0.1

Population density at special building types

Night-time building population density ($P_{n,b}$) is estimated making some special assumptions for hospitals and hotels. For the hospitals, a 20 % of the total employees is assumed to work during night-

time, while for hotels, a 10 % of the total employees are assumed to work during night-time. Moreover, an estimated amount of occupancy for both building types is added according to an empirical fixed volume density parameter (0.0015 inh./m³). The following equations are used instead of Eq. 2 for night-time building population density:

$$\text{Hospitals: } P_{n,b} = \left(0.2 \cdot M_B \cdot \frac{V_{wor,b}}{V_{wor,B}} + 0.0015 \cdot V_{wor,b} \right) / A_b \quad (\text{S.1})$$

$$\text{Hotels: } P_{n,b} = \left(0.1 \cdot M_B \cdot \frac{V_{wor,b}}{V_{wor,B}} + 0.0015 \cdot V_{wor,b} \right) / A_b \quad (\text{S.2})$$

For weekday daytime building population density ($P_{d,b}$), special assumptions are made for schools and university buildings, where, apart from the employees, the 30% of the total number of students of Basel University are assumed to be distributed across the buildings during day, while the total number of school students are assumed to be distributed across the school buildings according to their building volume. The following equations apply instead of Eq.3:

$$\text{University: } P_{d,b} = \left(0.85 \cdot M_B \cdot \frac{V_{wor,b}}{V_{wor,B}} + 0.3 \cdot U \cdot \frac{V_{wor,b}}{V_{uni,C}} \right) / A_b \quad (\text{S.3})$$

$$\text{Schools: } P_{d,b} = \left(0.85 \cdot M_B \cdot \frac{V_{wor,b}}{V_{wor,B}} + S \cdot \frac{V_{wor,b}}{V_{sch,C}} \right) / A_b \quad (\text{S.4})$$

U and $V_{uni,C}$ are the total number of students of the University of Basel (approximately 12,000 according to University statistics) and the total workspace volume of the university buildings across the city respectively. Accordingly, S and $V_{sch,C}$ are the total number of school students across the City of Basel (approximately 25,000 according to city statistics) and the total workspace volume of the school buildings across the city. Weekend daytime building population density ($P_{e,b}$) for schools and universities is assumed zero.

Road traffic data and statistical analysis

Traffic counts from the available station network (Fig. S.1, Table S.4) are used to estimate the hourly traffic for the whole study area according to the road type classification. Traffic on main and collecting roads is sufficiently monitored across the city by the existing stations, however the least frequented road types: ‘‘Settlement’’, ‘‘Tempo 30’’ and ‘‘Meeting areas’’ do not have permanent traffic counters. However, there are plenty of data from short-term traffic surveys of Basel-Stadt since 2010 (Verkehrszählungen, 2021) which are used to extract annual diurnal profiles (weekend and weekday) according to road types. This dataset provided the linear relationships, presented in Fig. S.2, between main road hourly traffic and the hourly traffic of settlement, tempo 30 and meeting area road types. These relationships are used to estimate the traffic of the road types with no permanent traffic counters according to the mean traffic counts of the permanent stations on main roads.

Figure S.1. Road classification for the study area and locations of the traffic stations.

Table S.4. Permanent traffic stations operated by Basel-Stadt. The first 11 stations in the list are inside the study area and their recordings are used for the respective road parts. The rest are used for the traffic statistics per road type.

No	Station Name	Latitude	Longitude	Area	Directions	Lanes	Street Type	Installation
1	Dreirosenbrücke lokal	47.571	7.583	Basel	2	4	Main	01/09/2012
2	Johanniterbrücke	47.565	7.588	Basel	2	2	Main	01/07/2004
3	Wettsteinbrücke	47.558	7.597	Basel	2	2	Main	01/01/2000
4	Luzernerring-Brücke	47.57	7.572	Basel	2	2	Main	01/01/2015
5	Heuwaage-Viadukt	47.552	7.587	Basel	2	4	Main	01/01/2001
6	Viaduktstrasse 60 (Rialto)	47.55	7.583	Basel	2	2	Main	01/01/2000
7	St. Alban-Anlage 72	47.553	7.605	Basel	2	2	Main	01/09/2000
8	Sevogelstrasse 82	47.549	7.601	Basel	1	1	Collecting	01/09/2000
9	Riehenring 120	47.567	7.598	Basel	2	2	Collecting	01/01/2000
10	Nauenstrasse 73	47.547	7.595	Basel	2	4	Main	01/10/2004
11	Flughafenstrasse 30	47.568	7.571	Basel	2	2	Main	01/04/2006
12	Hochbergerstrasse 55	47.577	7.597	Basel	2	2	Main	01/09/2000
13	Dorenbachviadukt	47.544	7.576	Basel	2	2	Main	01/01/2000
14	Wasgenring 62	47.562	7.564	Basel	2	4	Main	01/01/2000
15	Grenzacherstrasse 511	47.563	7.631	Basel	2	2	Main	01/01/2000
16	Fasanenstrasse (DB-Brücke)	47.574	7.603	Basel	2	4	Collecting	01/09/2000
17	Dornacherstrasse 49	47.545	7.586	Basel	1	2	Collecting	01/01/2000
18	Gundeldingerstrasse 107	47.543	7.585	Basel	1	2	Collecting	01/09/2000
19	Gundeldingerstrasse 428	47.538	7.6	Basel	1	1	Collecting	01/09/2000
20	Grosspeterstrasse 45	47.545	7.602	Basel	2	3	Main	01/09/2000

21	J. Burckhardt-Strasse 85	47.545	7.6	Basel	1	2	Main	01/09/2000
22	Elsässerstrasse 146	47.573	7.576	Basel	2	2	Collecting	01/08/2000
23	Schlachthofstrasse	47.577	7.567	Basel	2	2	Main	01/08/2000
24	Flughafenstrasse, Grenze	47.575	7.562	Basel	2	2	Main	01/10/2000
25	Zoll CH-D, Hiltalingerstrasse	47.589	7.593	Basel	2	2	Main	01/01/2000
26	Zoll CH-D, Freiburgerstrasse	47.581	7.605	Basel	2	2	Main	01/01/2000
27	Äussere Baselstrasse 381	47.572	7.624	Riehen	2	2	Main	01/01/2000
28	Bäumlihofstrasse	47.57	7.628	Riehen	2	2	Collecting	01/01/2000
29	Zoll CH-D, Weilstrasse	47.592	7.644	Riehen	2	2	Main	01/10/2015
30	Zoll CH-D, Lörracherstrasse	47.595	7.656	Lörrach	2	4	Main	01/01/2000
31	Zoll CH-D, Grenzacherstrasse	47.562	7.635	Grenzach2		6	Main	01/01/2000

Figure S.2. Linear regressions between the diurnal hourly profiles (weekend and weekday separately) of all available permanent and short-term traffic stations during 2010 – 2020, categorized as main roads, settlement roads, tempo 30 roads and meeting areas.

When it comes to road segments with measured traffic counts, the sum of all lanes is used in Eq. 8 as V_i . For the rest of the roads of the study area, traffic counts are estimated as vehicles per lane per hour (veh. lane⁻¹ h⁻¹) and it is uniformly assumed that the main and the main collecting roads have two lanes, while the rest of the road types have one lane, which is the most typical case across the study area.

Building energy consumption statistics

The CO₂ emissions from buildings in Basel are caused mainly by the fuel combustion for space and water heating. Additionally, there are emissions from buildings with commercial/industrial use that are not directly related to heating but to other commercial/industrial processes. Fuels used for the city's energy demand in total and specifically for building heating are summarized in Figure S.3. In the renewable sources part of the energy mix, water, wood, sun and environmental heat are included in the total energy mix, while for building heating, this category includes only wood and environmental

heating. From the energy mix for heating, one part of the fuel combustion is performed locally at building or neighborhood combustion units and the rest is consumed by the 4 major energy units across the city to produce district heating supply. District heating units use primarily city garbage, industrial waste, wood and natural gas as fuels (Energiestatistik Basel-Stadt, 2020).

Figure S.3. Source mix of the total energy consumption (mobility fuels excluded) and for building heating in the canton of Basel-Stadt for the year 2016 (Sources: Energiestatistik Basel-Stadt, 2020; Kantonaler Richtplan Teilrichtplan Energie, 2020)

The center of the city is well-connected to the district heating network, covering on average around 75 % of the total building heating demand (Kantonaler Richtplan Teilrichtplan Energie, 2020). Areas outside the district heating network are mainly the south and east part of Basel-Stadt, where the building heating demand is covered by local combustion units, using mainly gas and heating oil. Fig. S.4 presents the energy source mix for building heating per district across the city centre and inside the study area. The data refer to the reference year 2016 (Kantonaler Richtplan Teilrichtplan Energie, 2020). Fig. S.5 presents the energy mix used by buildings for the reference years 2010, 2012, 2014, 2016 and 2018 for the whole Basel-Stadt area (Energiestatistik Basel-Stadt, 2020). It is evident that district heating covers nearly half of the residential energy demand for heating (concerning the whole Basel-Stadt), while the rest is covered mainly by gas and oil, as also shown in Fig. S.4. Since 2018, district heating coverage has increased in the residential domain and gas consumption locally has decreased, indicating less emissions occurring locally inside the city centre. In Fig. S.5, the energy use of the commercial/industrial sector is presented separately from the residential. Moreover, the total Heating Degree Hours (HDH) of each year is presented in Fig. S.5 for comparison. It is evident that the energy use by the residential sector follows the yearly HDH, whereas energy consumed by the commercial/industrial sector shows a continuous decreasing trend over the years, not related to the yearly HDH. It is important to note that the majority of the energy consumption of the commercial/industrial sector occurs outside the study area.

Figure S.4. Building heating energy demand broken down by energy source in the respective districts of the city centre. Data consider the year 2016. In yellow, the areas classified as commercial/industrial by Urban Atlas 2018 are shown. In the northern and central residential districts of Basel, district heating accounts for around three quarters of the total heating requirement. The heat demand in the other residential districts of Basel as well as in Riehen and Bettingen, on the other hand, is largely covered by the energy sources heating oil and gas (Source: Kantonaler Richtplan Teilrichtplan Energie, 2020).

Figure S.5. Annual statistics of the energy used from the residential and the commercial sectors as opposed to the total Heating Degree Hours of each year. Commercial sector includes also the industrial sector. (Source: Energiestatistik Basel-Stadt, 2020)

Average monthly HDH time-series are presented in Fig. S.6a. Fig. S.6b presents the monthly energy consumption for district heating distributed across the whole network of the Energy Supplier Company (IWB) (Energiestatistik Basel-Stadt, 2020). This dataset concerns the total consumption, meaning that it includes both residential and commercial/industrial sectors. The dataset, as presented in Fig S.6b, is normalized for space heating consumption by subtracting 30 GWh (close to the absolute minimum, when monthly HDH = 0) from each monthly value. This normalization serves to reflect better the energy consumption variability for space heating and reduce the effects of the commercial/industrial consumption that is not related to building heating. This dataset is then used as a proxy to estimate the total monthly consumption for building heating by the residential sector (Fig. S.6b) by comparing the yearly sums of this time-series for the reference years 2010, 2012, 2014, 2016 and 2018 to the official reports of the statistical authorities (Fig. S.5). A single conversion coefficient is established for each reference year, applied to the monthly values of each respective time period. Interestingly, the conversion coefficient showed a consistent declining trend (2010 and 2012: 1.5, 2014 and 2016: 1.4, 2018: 1.2), reflecting the gradual proportional increase of using district heating for covering the heating demand of the residential sector (Fig. S.5). It is already obvious from visually inspecting Fig.S.6 that the monthly energy use for heating is very closely related to the monthly average HDH.

Figure S.6. Time-series of (a) monthly mean and standard deviation of Heating Degree Hours (HDH) for the area of Basel, (b) monthly energy consumption for district heating (residential + commercial/industrial) and estimated total energy consumption for heating by the residential sector of Basel-Stadt.

The monthly estimated energy consumption for residential heating (in GWh) is converted to mean hourly consumption (in Wh) and then divided by the total occupied building volume for residential use in the city of Basel-Stadt area for each respective year to express the consumption per building volume (Wh m^{-3}). The regression between the estimated mean hourly consumption per building volume and monthly average HDH for the period 2005 – 2020 (Fig. S.7) reveals that the heating consumption by residential buildings is nearly linearly dependent on the HDH. The regression of Fig. S.7 is used in the

building emission model (Eq. 5) to estimate energy consumption for space heating per building volume (W m^{-3}) according to HDH.

Figure S.7. Regression between Heating Degree Hours (HDH) and building energy consumption for heating of the residential sector expressed per m^3 of building volume.

Biogenic flux model constants

Table S.5. List of constants in the biogenic models, along with their units, a short description, the equations involved and the references used for determining their value. Literature values regarding temperate deciduous broadleaved trees and grasses are mainly considered, where relevant, which are the main plant types in the study area.

Parameter	Value	Units	Description	Equations	References
A_{max}	10	$\mu\text{mol CO}_2 \text{ m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$	maximum leaf gross photosynthetic rate	14, B.1	Larcher, 2003
α	0.045	$\text{mol CO}_2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$ PAR	quantum yield for CO_2 assimilation	13, B.1	Rogers et al., 2017
α_1	25	N/A	empirical coefficient in Leuning (1995) model	B.4	Leuning, 1995
b	0.5	N/A	empirical coefficient in β -factor formula	16	Liss et al., 2009
b_1	5	N/A	empirical coefficient	B.4	this study
c_s	400	$\mu\text{mol CO}_2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$ air	CO_2 concentration at the leaf surface	B.4	Leuning, 1995
D_o	0.15	kPa	empirically determined coefficient for the VPD scalar inside Leuning (1995) model	B.4	Leuning, 1995
E_o	383	K	temperature sensitivity parameter for soil respiration	16	Liss et al., 2009
g_o	0.01	$\text{mol CO}_2 \text{ m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$	residual stomatal conductance for CO_2 (g_s when $A_{net} = 0$, $\text{PAR} = 0$).	B.4	Leuning, 1995
J_{max}	70	$\mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$	potential rate of whole-chain electron transport	B.1 (adapted)	Leuning, 1995

K_c	302	$\mu\text{mol CO}_2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$ air	Michaelis constant for CO_2	B.5	Leuning, 1995
k_d	0.7	N/A	radiation extinction coefficient within plant canopies for diffuse radiation	A.5, A.7, A.8	Campbell and Norman, 1998; De Pury and Farquhar, 1997; Spitters, 1986
K_o	256	$\text{mmol O}_2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$ air	Michaelis constant for O_2	B.5	Leuning, 1995
Q_{10}	1.85	N/A	temperature sensitivity of leaf respiration	B.3	Heskel et al., 2016
$R_{l,ref}$	1.73	$\mu\text{mol CO}_2 \text{ m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$	reference leaf respiration at $T_{air} = 25 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$	B.3	Heskel et al., 2016
$R_{S,ref}$	2.4	$\mu\text{mol CO}_2 \text{ m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$	reference soil respiration at $T_{soil} = 10 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$	16	Liss et al., 2009
o_i	210	$\text{mmol O}_2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$ air	intercellular O_2 concentration	B.5	Farquhar et al., 1980
T_{opt}	23	$^\circ\text{C}$	optimum air temperature for gross photosynthesis	B.2	Larcher, 2003
T_o	-46	$^\circ\text{C}$	low-temperature limit for soil respiration	16	Lloyd and Taylor, 1994
$T_{ref,S}$	10	$^\circ\text{C}$	reference soil temperature for soil respiration	16	Lloyd and Taylor, 1994
$T_{ref,l}$	25	$^\circ\text{C}$	reference air temperature for leaf respiration	B.3	Heskel et al., 2016
V_{cmax}	40	$\mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$	maximum catalytic activity of Rubisco	B.5	Leuning, 1995; Rogers et al., 2017
W	10	$^\circ\text{C}$	width of the bell-shape curve at $f(T_{air}) = 0.5$	B.2	Larcher, 2003
Γ	40	$\mu\text{mol CO}_2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$ air	CO_2 compensation point (c_i when $A_{net} = 0$)	B.4, B.5	Larcher, 2003; Rogers et al., 2017
θ_{ref}	0.4	$\text{m}^3 \text{ m}^{-3}$	saturated soil volumetric water content	16, B.4	Liss et al., 2009
θ_g	0.1	$\text{m}^3 \text{ m}^{-3}$	minimum soil volumetric water content, limit to g_s	B.4	this study
θ_o	0.04	$\text{m}^3 \text{ m}^{-3}$	minimum soil volumetric water content, limit to R_s	16	Liss et al., 2009
ρ_l	0.1	N/A	leaf reflectance at PAR	A.4 – A.8	Jones, 2013
ρ_b	0.2	N/A	built material reflectance at PAR (approximation)	A.7	this study

Temporal variability of model outputs

A detailed overview of the seasonal and diurnal variability of the model outputs is presented in this section, where the behavior of the different urban source/sink components can be compared and where their contribution to the net CO_2 flux per season (Fig. S.8) and time of day (Fig. S.9) can be easily examined. It is clearly demonstrated that the building emissions ($E_B + E_C$) dominate the total F_C across the study area, especially during winter (Figs. S.8, S.9a,b). During summer, the net F_C (Fig. S.8a) is nearly half compared to winter and is largely defined by building ($E_B + E_C$), traffic (E_V) and human respiration (R_H) emissions (Fig. S.8b). The biogenic components influence the F_C mainly during spring and summer months (Fig. S.8c), while during daytime hours the net F_C is significantly decreased due

to photosynthesis (Fig. S.9b,c). During weekdays around noon, the emissions are offset by nearly 1/3 due to photosynthesis, while during weekends the offset is about 1/2 (Fig. S.9b,c).

Figure S.8. Time-series of the mean daily modelled CO₂ fluxes for the study area in 2018. (a) Net CO₂ flux (F_C), (b) anthropogenic emissions (building: $E_B + E_C$, traffic: E_V , human respiration: R_H), (c) biogenic flux components (soil respiration: R_S , plant respiration: R_V , plant photosynthesis: P_V).

Figure S.9. Diurnal hourly mean profiles of each modelled CO_2 flux component and the total F_C for the study area for the periods: (a) winter weekdays, (b) winter weekends, (c) summer weekdays, (d) summer weekends. Building: E_B , commercial/Industrial: E_C , traffic: E_V , human respiration: R_H , soil respiration: R_S , plant respiration: R_V , plant photosynthesis: P_V .

Biogenic flux model sensitivity

The biogenic flux model sensitivity to the uncertainties of three key inputs (LAI, A_{max} , θ) over different land cover types was tested by running the model across the study area with perturbed parameterizations of the above inputs. Different LAI and A_{max} variabilities between trees and grasses have been considered. Specifically, the uncertainty of LAI over trees was set $\pm 1 \text{ m}^2 \text{ m}^{-2}$ around the estimated value and over grasses from 0 to -40% of the estimated value. The A_{max} of grasses was considered to vary between 0 and +100% of the original value (i.e. $10 - 20 \mu\text{mol CO}_2 \text{ m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$), while the respective A_{max} of trees was kept constant to $10 \mu\text{mol CO}_2 \text{ m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$. The uncertainty in the spatial variability of θ was simulated by adding an error range of $\pm 0.1 \text{ m}^3 \text{ m}^{-3}$ to the measured values of the three stations (Table S.3). The uncertainty ranges of the parameters were defined based on comparisons with relevant literature (e.g. Breuer et al., 2003; Larcher, 2003; Jarvi et al., 2011). The simulations were run by i. changing only one of the three parameters at a time, and ii. by generating random combinations of all parameter variabilities.

Figure S.10. Time-series of the mean daily modelled biogenic CO_2 fluxes for the study area in 2018 according to the original model parameterisation and the sensitivity analysis simulations (soil respiration: R_S , plant respiration: R_V , plant photosynthesis: $-P_V$, $\text{NEE} = R_S + R_V - P_V$). Bold lines represent the original parameterisation and the shaded areas around each line represent the range between maximum and minimum estimation according to the variability inserted in (a) LAI, (b) A_{max} and (c) θ . The shaded areas in (d) represent the 10 – 90 % percentile range of the estimations according to the random combinations of all perturbed parameters.

The uncertainties in LAI estimation affected R_V and P_V (Fig. S.10a), with annual estimates of R_V ranging from 0.2 to 0.9 $\text{kg CO}_2 \text{ m}^{-2} \text{ a}^{-1}$ and for P_V between -1.1 and -2.4 $\text{kg CO}_2 \text{ m}^{-2} \text{ a}^{-1}$. However, since the two components counterbalance in the net exchange, the resulting net biogenic flux range is between 0.1 and -0.5 $\text{kg CO}_2 \text{ m}^{-2} \text{ a}^{-1}$ (Table S.6). This range translates to a contribution to the net annual urban flux (including the anthropogenic components) between 0.5 and -2.8 %. The uncertainties simulated in grass A_{max} intended to evaluate how the model would work if the different land cover types were treated separately in the model parameterization. Grass photosynthetic capacities are highly variable and can reach much higher values than temperate deciduous broadleaved trees (Larcher, 2003). The A_{max} simulations affected only P_V towards higher absolute values (Fig. S.10b), removing at maximum an extra -0.4 $\text{kg CO}_2 \text{ m}^{-2} \text{ a}^{-1}$ from the total annual budget in the extreme case where A_{grass} is set to 20 $\mu\text{mol CO}_2 \text{ m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$ throughout the year. The effect to the net annual urban flux, compared to the original model parameterisation, would be only 2 % (Table S.6). The variability of θ affects mainly the R_S component and secondarily P_V (Fig. S.10c). θ variability is mainly driving the net biogenic exchange towards zero and positive values because high soil moisture induces higher R_S , while extremely dry conditions reduce both R_S and P_V absolute values. The net contributions of the θ variability to the total fluxes is around 2.1 % (Table S.6).

The simulations under random combinations of the perturbed parameters give a more comprehensive overview of the model sensitivity to LAI, A_{max} and θ uncertainties (Fig. S.10d). Overall, P_V is the most sensitive component, followed by R_V (Fig. S.11). R_S is the least sensitive to the perturbed parameters. Depending on the parametrization, the biogenic components of the study area act mainly as a C sink of various strengths, but under extreme parametrizations they could even act as a weak source (Fig. S.11). Nevertheless, such variability in the biogenic components is hardly noticeable in the total urban balance when the anthropogenic emissions are taken into account, contributing between a range of 0.5 and -2.8 % (Table S.6). In conclusion, a simple parameterization of the biogenic model is considered sufficient to meet the purposes of an urban CO₂ flux study.

Table S.6. The variability of the annual modeled biogenic fluxes of the study area for 2018 (kg CO₂ m⁻² a⁻¹) according to the sensitivity analysis. The first column presents the results for the unperturbed modeled parameters (original), the second, third and fourth columns present the maximum and minimum annual fluxes according to the inserted variability in the parameters LAI, A_{max} and θ respectively. The last column (all) presents the 90 % and 10 % percentiles of the results by the random combinations between all perturbed parameters. The percentages in parentheses show the contributions to the net annual urban flux including the anthropogenic components.

		Original	LAI	A_{max}	θ	All
Soil respiration	R_S	1.0 (5.5 %)	--	--	1.3 (7.0 %)	1.2 (6.4 %)
Plant respiration	R_V	0.6 (3.3 %)	0.9 (5.0 %)	--	--	0.8 (4.3 %)
Plant photosynthesis	P_V	-1.9 (-10.4 %)	-1.1 (-5.9 %)	-1.9 (-10.4 %)	-1.1 (-5.9 %)	-1.1 (-5.9 %)
Net biogenic exchange (NEE)		-0.3 (-1.6 %)	0.1 (0.5 %)	-0.3 (-1.6 %)	0.1 (0.5 %)	0.1 (0.5 %)
			-0.5 (-2.8 %)	-0.7 (-3.6 %)	-0.3 (-1.6 %)	-0.5 (-2.8 %)

Figure S.11. Boxplots of the annual flux estimates of soil respiration (R_S), plant respiration (R_V), plant photosynthesis ($-P_V$) and NEE ($R_S + R_V - P_V$) according to the random combinations of all parameter variabilities of the biogenic model sensitivity analysis.

Model computational characteristics

The model is implemented in MATLAB® (ver. R2019b, The MathWorks Inc., Natick, Massachusetts, USA). The computational speed for the study area (3,040 m x 2,980 m) is approximately 2.5 s per time step. At an hourly time step, a full year is simulated at around 6.1 hours. This estimation is made on a desktop pc with Intel® Core™ i9-10900 CPU @ 2.80GHz, 10 Core(s), 20 Logical Processor(s), 64 GB RAM. The time needed for loading the inputs and writing the outputs on a disk is not considered in the above estimation. Most of the computational time (~70 %) is occupied by the gross photosynthesis model. The computational time of the latter depends on the area which is occupied by vegetation and the daylight duration, therefore it is much faster in winter compared to summer. Moreover, the model computational time is expected to increase proportionally to the model domain, mainly due to the gross photosynthesis model architecture.

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